

Two new Fuzzy Models Using Fuzzy Cognitive Maps Model and Kosko Hamming Distance

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Abstract

In this paper for the first time two new fuzzy models viz Merged Fuzzy Cognitive Maps (MFCMs) models and Specially Merged Linked Fuzzy Cognitive Maps (SMLFCMs) are introduced. To compare the experts opinion a new techniques called Kosko Hamming distance and Kosko Hamming weight are introduced.

Key words : Merged graphs, Fuzzy Cognitive Maps, Merged matrices, Merged Fuzzy Cognitive Maps (MFCMs), Specially Merged Linked Fuzzy Cognitive Maps (SMLFCMs), Kosko Hamming Distance

1. Introduction

This paper has six sections. The first section is introductory in nature. In the second section the concept of merged graphs and merged matrices are recalled from¹¹. For the notion of Fuzzy Cognitive Maps model and its application to social problems please refer¹⁻¹¹. In section three the new notion of Merged FCM is introduced and illustrated by an example. Section four introduces the new Specially Merged Linked FCM model. Section five introduces the new technique of comparing the views of the experts using the Kosko Hamming distance and Kosko Hamming weight. The final section gives the conclusion obtained from this research.

2 Merged Graphs and their Merged Matrices :

In this section the definition and properties of merged graphs and their merged matrices are recalled. This is illustrated by examples. For more about merged graphs please refer¹¹.

Definition 2.1: Let $G_1 = \{V_1, E_1\}$ and $G_2 = \{V_2, E_2\}$ be two graphs with V_i vertex set and E_i edge set of G_i ; $i = 1, 2$. We can merge one or more vertices of G_1 with G_2 and or one or more edges of G_1 with G_2 which are common to G_1 and G_2 . The resultant graph got so by merging common vertices

(and or) common edges is a graph defined as the merged graph.

We will illustrate this definition by an example.

Example 2.1: Let G_1 be the directed graph given in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1

The matrix related with G_1 given in Figure 2.1 be M_1 , M_1 is as follows:

$$M_1 = \begin{matrix} & v_1 & v_2 & v_3 & v_5 & v_6 & v_7 \\ \begin{matrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ v_3 \\ v_5 \\ v_6 \\ v_7 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}.$$

Let G_2 be the directed graph which is given in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2

Let M_2 be the matrix associated with the directed graph G_2 given in Figure 2.2.

$$M_2 = \begin{matrix} & v_1 & v_4 & v_5 & v_8 & v_9 \\ \begin{matrix} v_1 \\ v_4 \\ v_5 \\ v_8 \\ v_9 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}.$$

Let G be the merged graph of the directed graphs G_1 and G_2 given in Figure 2.3 got by merging the edge v_1v_5 and the vertices v_1 and v_5 . The merged graph G is depicted in Figure 2.3 in the following:

Figure 2.3

Let the matrix M denote the merged matrices; M_1 and M_2 and is the matrix associated with the merged directed graph G which is given in Figure 2.3.

$$M = \begin{matrix} & v_1 & v_2 & v_3 & v_4 & v_5 & v_6 & v_7 & v_8 & v_9 \\ \begin{matrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ v_3 \\ v_4 \\ v_5 \\ v_6 \\ v_7 \\ v_8 \\ v_9 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}.$$

This is the way two graphs are merged and the merging is unique and their related matrices are merged and matrix so obtained is defined as the merged matrix.

Next the notion of specially merged linked graph is described by an example.

Example 2.2: Let G_1 , G_2 and G_3 be the three directed graphs given in the following figures 2.4, 2.5 and 2.6.

Figure 2.4

Let M_1 be the matrix associated with the graph G_1 ,

$$M_1 = \begin{matrix} & v_1 & v_2 & v_3 & v_4 \\ \begin{matrix} v_1 \\ v_2 \\ v_3 \\ v_4 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}.$$

Let G_2 be the directed graph given in Figure 2.5.

Figure 2.5

Let M_2 be the matrix associated with the graph G_2 ,

$$M_2 = \begin{matrix} & v_3 & v_4 & v_5 & v_6 \\ \begin{matrix} v_3 \\ v_4 \\ v_5 \\ v_6 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}.$$

Let G_3 be the directed graph given in Figure 2.6.

This sort of merging more than two graphs under certain constraints is known as the specially merged linked graphs.

In the next section how these concepts are used in the construction of merged FCMs is described.

3 Definition of New Merged FCMs and their properties :

In this section the notion of Merged Fuzzy Cognitive Maps (MFCMs) is introduced. Merged FCMs are built using the concept of merged graphs and the related merged matrices and described by an example.

Definition 3.1: Let $C = \{C_1, \dots, C_n\}$ be the n nodes associated with a real world problem. Suppose t experts want to work with this problem using FCMs but only using some selected nodes from the set of nodes C .

Let the directed graphs given by the t experts be G_1, G_2, \dots, G_t such that the vertex set of the graph G_i with G_j is non empty for $i \neq j$; $G_i \cap G_j \neq \phi$; $1 \leq i, j \leq t$. Then we can merge some graphs say k of them, $k \leq t$ from G_1, \dots, G_t so that the vertices of all these graphs give all the nodes of the set C .

Let G be the merged graph and the FCMs associated with G will be known as the Merged Fuzzy Cognitive Maps (MFCMs) and the connection matrix associated with G will be known as the merged connection matrix of the MFCMs or the merged dynamical system of the FCMs.

We will first illustrate this situation by an example.

Example 3.1: Let us suppose we have $C = \{C_1, C_2, C_3, \dots, C_{12}\}$ to be the set of nodes/attributes associated with a problem. Let five experts work with the problem using FCMs and the nodes from the set C .

Suppose the first expert wants to work with the set of nodes given by X_1 where $X_1 = \{C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4, C_8\} \subseteq C$ and the second expert wishes to work with the set of nodes given by X_2 , where $X_2 = \{C_3, C_7, C_5, C_{12}\} \subseteq C$.

The third expert works with the set of nodes given by the subset X_3 , where $X_3 = \{C_1, C_7, C_{10}, C_{11}\} \subseteq C$. Let the fourth expert work with the nodes $C_6, C_9, C_1, C_{10}, C_{12}$ given by the set $X_4 = \{C_6, C_9, C_1, C_{10}, C_{12}\} \subseteq C$.

The fifth expert works with $X_5 = \{C_6, C_5, C_{10}, C_2, C_9, C_7\} \subseteq C$. Now we can get the merged FCMs in two ways. Taking the nodes $X_1 \cup X_2 \cup X_3 \cup X_4$ so that we get the merged graph G of the graphs G_1, G_2, G_3 and G_4 or $X_1 \cup X_2 \cup X_3 \cup X_5$ that is we get the merged graph G' of the graphs G_1, G_2, G_3 and G_5 .

So we get two integrated merged FCMs model to work with. Let us consider the directed graphs given by the five experts.

Let G_1 be the directed graph given in Figure 3.1 by the first expert using the set of attributes X_1 .

Figure 3.1

Let M_1 be the matrix associated with the graph G_1 .

$$M_1 = \begin{matrix} & C_1 & C_2 & C_3 & C_4 & C_8 \\ \begin{matrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \\ C_3 \\ C_4 \\ C_8 \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}.$$

Let G_2 be the directed graph given by the second expert using the attributes $X_2 = \{C_3, C_7, C_5, C_{12}\}$ given in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2

Let M_2 be the matrix associated with the graph G_2 .

$$M_2 = \begin{matrix} & C_3 & C_5 & C_7 & C_{12} \\ \begin{matrix} C_3 \\ C_5 \\ C_7 \\ C_{12} \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}.$$

Let G_3 be the directed graph given in Figure 3.3 given by the third expert using the nodes $X_3 = \{C_1, C_7, C_{10}, C_{11}\}$;

Figure 3.3

Let M_3 be the matrix associated with the graph G_3 .

$$M_3 = \begin{matrix} & C_1 & C_7 & C_{10} & C_{11} \\ \begin{matrix} C_1 \\ C_7 \\ C_{10} \\ C_{11} \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}.$$

Let G_4 be the directed graph provided

by the fourth expert using the set of nodes $X_4 = \{C_6, C_9, C_1, C_{12}, C_{10}\}$ given in Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4

Let M_4 be the matrix associated with the graph G_4 .

$$M_4 = \begin{matrix} & C_1 & C_6 & C_9 & C_{10} & C_{12} \\ \begin{matrix} C_1 \\ C_6 \\ C_9 \\ C_{10} \\ C_{12} \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}.$$

Using $X_5 = \{C_6, C_5, C_{10}, C_2, C_9, C_7\}$, let G_5 be the directed associated with the fifth expert given in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5

Let M_5 be the matrix associated with the graph G_5 .

$$M_5 = \begin{matrix} & C_2 & C_5 & C_6 & C_7 & C_9 & C_{10} \\ \begin{matrix} C_2 \\ C_5 \\ C_6 \\ C_7 \\ C_9 \\ C_{10} \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}.$$

Let M_1, M_2, \dots, M_5 be the matrices associated with the graphs G_1, G_2, \dots, G_5 respectively. Let the merged matrix of the matrices be M which is also the merged connection matrix M of the specially linked merged graph G given in Figure 3.6.

Now to get the integrated merged FCMs we have to merge the graphs G_1, G_2, G_3 and G_4 or G_1, G_2, G_3 and G_5 . So we get in total using merged FCMs two integrated merged FCMs using all the 12 attributes. The merged graph G of the experts 1 to 4 is given in Figure 3.6.

Figure 3.6

Using this merged connection matrices M_1, M_2, M_3 and M_4 of graphs G_1, G_2, G_3 and G_4 respectively we can study the integrated merged dynamical system of the integrated MFCMs.

$$M = \begin{matrix} & C_1 & C_2 & C_3 & C_4 & C_5 & C_6 & C_7 & C_8 & C_9 & C_{10} & C_{11} & C_{12} \\ \begin{matrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \\ C_3 \\ C_4 \\ C_5 \\ C_6 \\ C_7 \\ C_8 \\ C_9 \\ C_{10} \\ C_{11} \\ C_{12} \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}.$$

Now using the experts 1, 2, 3, and 5 we get the merged graph G' of the four directed graphs of the FCM given in Figure 3.7.

Figure 3.7

Let the merged connection matrix of the matrices M_1, M_2, M_3 and M_5 of the merged graph G' of Figure 3.3.7 be M' which is as follows:

$$M' = \begin{matrix} & C_1 & C_2 & C_3 & C_4 & C_5 & C_6 & C_7 & C_8 & C_9 & C_{10} & C_{11} & C_{12} \\ \begin{matrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \\ C_3 \\ C_4 \\ C_5 \\ C_6 \\ C_7 \\ C_8 \\ C_9 \\ C_{10} \\ C_{11} \\ C_{12} \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}.$$

Thus we can find the merged connection matrix M' of the FCM and study the problem. The advantages of using this new merged FCMs models are;

1. Experts can choose any number of attributes from the given set of attributes so that they can be free to do work with the problem with their choice.
2. When the number of attributes is a small number; working is easy and apt.
3. While getting merged model by combining all the experts opinion (so no expert is left out), everyone is given the same degree of importance.
4. By combining them differently using different sets of experts we get several merged FCMs for the same problem.
5. The values in the connection merged

integrated matrices need not be thresholded for they take only values from the set $\{-1, 1, 0\}$.

4 Definition and Description of Specially Merged Linked FCMs :

The Specially Merged Linked Fuzzy Cognitive Maps (SMLFCMs) model are defined and described in the following.

Definition 4.1: Let $C = \{C_1, \dots, C_n\}$ be the n attributes of a problem with which t experts E_1, E_2, \dots, E_t work using FCMs model. Each of the experts work with X_i set of attributes from the n attribute set C ; that is $X_i \subseteq C$, X_i the subset of C . Now the sets X_i 's $1 \leq i \leq t$ are so formed such that $X_i \cap X_{i+1} \neq \phi$, $X_i \cap X_j = \phi$, for $j = 3, 4, \dots, t$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, t-1$. That is $X_1 \cap X_2 \neq \phi$, $X_2 \cap X_3 \neq \phi$ but $X_2 \cap X_i = \phi$, for $i = 4, 5, 6, \dots, t$; similarly is $X_3 \cap X_4 \neq \phi$ but $X_3 \cap X_i = \phi$, for $i = 5, 6, \dots, t$ and so on.

Thus we see even when G_1, G_2, \dots, G_t are the directed graphs given by the experts E_1, E_2, \dots, E_t using the set of nodes X_1, X_2, \dots, X_t respectively we see we cannot merge any G_i with G_j . G_i can be merged with G_j provided $j = i+1$ or $i-1$ ($i \neq 1$). Thus we defined this special type of merging as specially merged linked graphs. Let M_1, M_2, \dots, M_n be the n matrices associated with the directed graphs G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n respectively. Let M be the specially merged linked matrix associated with the specially merged linked graph.

We call the FCMs associated with these specially merged linked graphs are defined as Specially Merged Linked Fuzzy Cognitive Maps (SMLFCMs) model.

We will illustrate this situation by an example.

Example 4.1: Let $C = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_{11}\}$ be the collection of nodes associated with a problem. Let three experts E_1, E_2 and E_3 work with the same problem using the FCMs model choosing a few nodes from C . Let the expert E_1 choose to work with the nodes $X_1 = \{C_1, C_2, C_3, C_7, C_8\} \subseteq C$.

Let the expert E_2 work with the nodes $X_2 = \{C_1, C_6, C_7, C_4, C_9\} \subseteq C$ and the expert E_3 chooses to work with the nodes $X_3 = \{C_5, C_6, C_{10}, C_{11}, C_4\}$.

Let G_1, G_2 and G_3 be the directed graphs associated with the experts E_1, E_2 and E_3 respectively given in Figures 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3.

Figure 4.1

is the directed graph given in Figure 4.1 of the FCMs given by the first expert.

Figure 4.2

Let G_2 be the directed graph of the FCMs given by the second expert as given in Figure 4.2.

Let G_3 be the directed graph given by the third expert which is given in the following Figure 4.3:

Figure 4.3

Let

$$M_1 = \begin{matrix} & C_1 & C_2 & C_3 & C_7 & C_8 \\ C_1 & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ C_2 & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \\ C_3 & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ C_7 & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ C_8 & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}, M_2 = \begin{matrix} & C_1 & C_4 & C_6 & C_7 & C_9 \\ C_1 & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \\ C_4 & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ C_6 & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \\ C_7 & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ C_9 & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

and

$$M_3 = \begin{matrix} & C_4 & C_5 & C_6 & C_{10} & C_{11} \\ C_4 & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ C_5 & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ C_6 & \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\ C_{10} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \\ C_{11} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

be the connection matrices associated with the directed graphs G_1 , G_2 and G_3 respectively given in Figures 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3.

Now we see we cannot merge G_1 and G_3 as they do not have a common node or an edge. Now we can merge only in one way G_1 with G_2 and G_2 with G_3 which is the specially linked merged graph G given in the following Figure 4.4.

Figure 4.4

Let M_I denote the specially linked merged matrix of the matrices M_1 , M_2 and M_3 of the directed graphs G_1 , G_2 and G_3 . Using G we can find the integrated merged linked special connection matrix M of the

specially merged linked matrices of the matrices M_1 , M_2 and M_3 which is also the connection matrix of the specially linked graph G of the dynamical system. That matrix will serve as the dynamical system of the specially merged linked FCMs model given in the following.

The matrix M of G is got by merging M_1 , M_2 and M_3 is as follows:

$$M_I = \begin{matrix} & C_1 & C_2 & C_3 & C_4 & C_5 & C_6 & C_7 & C_8 & C_9 & C_{10} & C_{11} \\ \begin{matrix} C_1 \\ C_2 \\ C_3 \\ C_4 \\ C_5 \\ C_6 \\ C_7 \\ C_8 \\ C_9 \\ C_{10} \\ C_{11} \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix}.$$

Next we proceed on to define Kosko Hamming distance function in the next section.

5 Kosko Hamming Distance Function and Kosko Hamming Weight :

We know Hamming distance measures the number of coordinates a row vector $1 \times n$ differs from another $1 \times n$ row vector. So in the vector space $V^n = \{(a_1, \dots, a_n) \mid a_i \in F; 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ defined over the field F we can define the Hamming distance for any $x, y \in V^n$ as $d(x, y) =$ number of coordinates in which x

and y differ.

However in case of Kosko Hamming distance function we can define the distance function d_k only if these conditions are satisfied.

1. We need to have basically a fuzzy model say a FCMs model.
2. We need atleast two experts working with the same number of concepts/nodes using only the same type of fuzzy model with same set of attributes on the same problem say for instance a FCM model.
3. We can define the Kosko Hamming distance function d_k on the resultant state vectors given by two experts that is on the hidden pattern of a same initial state vector X_i used by both the experts using FCMs model.

So the concept of Kosko Hamming distance cannot be defined for any resultant state vectors but only those resultant state vectors whose initial input state vector is the same. Thus Kosko Hamming distance is distinctly different from the Hamming distance. This d_k also measures only the number of places in which the resultant state vectors given by two experts for the same initial state vector differs.

Now we proceed onto define the notion of Kosko Hamming distance.

Definition 5.1: Let some t experts E_1, E_2, \dots, E_t work with the same problem using the same set of attributes or nodes $C = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n\}$ using FCMs model.

Let M_1, M_2, \dots, M_t be the t ($n \times n$) connection matrices of the FCMs associated

with the experts E_1, E_2, \dots, E_t respectively. Suppose X be the initial state vector for which the hidden patterns using the dynamical system M_1, M_2, \dots, M_t is given by Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_t respectively. Now the Kosko Hamming distance function d_k is defined as $d_k(Y_i, Y_j) = \text{number of coordinates in which } Y_i \text{ is different from } Y_j; i \neq j; i \leq i, j \leq t; 0 \leq d_k(Y_i, Y_j) \leq n - 1$.

The use of this function is that it measures the closeness or the non closeness of the resultant vectors of two experts for the same initial state vector X of the problem.

So if the deviation, that is the value of $d_k(Y_i, Y_j)$ is very high we can analyse the experts E_i and E_j separately for that initial point X as well as for the other initial points also. If the functional value $d_k(Y_i, Y_j)$ is small we accept that both the experts hold the same view for the particular initial state vector X .

Definition 5.2: Let the experts, nodes and connection matrices be as in definition 5.1.

Let the initial state vector be X , Y_1, \dots, Y_t be the hidden patterns given by the dynamical systems M_1, M_2, \dots, M_t respectively. The Kosko Hamming weight function is defined and denoted by $w_k(Y_i) = d_k(Y_i, X)$; number of coordinates in which Y_i differs from X ; $i = 1, \dots, t$.

This new notion of Kosko Hamming weight function helps one in finding the impact of the particular node/nodes in X which are

taken in the on state over the dynamical system that is over the other nodes. If $w_k(Y_i)$ is very large it implies that the node has a very high impact on the system that is on other nodes which it has made to on state by its on state.

If $w_k(Y_i)$ is small it implies the node/nodes are taken in the on state has no impact on the other nodes or equivalently no impact over the system.

6. Conclusions

In this chapter we have introduced two new mathematical tools to study and analyse the FCMs model, the relation between the experts opinion and the impact on one node over other nodes in that dynamical system. Both the models can give the integrated view of all the experts. This model thus saves time. This model satisfies all experts because all are given equal status about the problem¹²⁻¹³.

The first tool helps in replacing the combined FCMs and makes the working easy by considering less number of attributes by getting the integrated merged FCMs model or special integrated linked merged FCMs model. The former can give more than one FCMs model so that comparison can be made, however the latter technique can give only one integrated merged FCMs model. Finally the tool of Kosko Hamming distance function and Kosko Hamming weight function can study the influence of a node over other nodes and the comparison of experts view on the problem.

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